

SUBSTITUTED DICARBOXYLIC ACIDS. PART I. SYNTHESIS OF
2-METHOXY-5-CHLORO-, 3-CHLORO-4-METHOXY- AND
3:4-DICHLORO-PHENYLSUCCINIC ACIDS

BY D. K. GENSE AND J. J. TRIVEDI

Several substituted phenylsuccinic acids have been synthesised using Lapworth's method.

Substituted succinic acids were required in this laboratory in connection with the synthesis of physiologically active compounds. Lapworth's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 49, 1699, 2741; 1925, 560) is convenient for synthesising substituted succinic acids from the appropriate aldehydes. Dave, Trivedi and Nargund (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1938, 7, 191) utilised it to prepare 3:4-dimethoxyphenylsuccinic acid from veratraldehyde. In this paper we have synthesised the substituted phenylsuccinic acids using 2-methoxy-5-chloro-, 3-chloro-4-methoxy- and 3:4-dichloro-benzaldehydes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium cyanoacetate solution was prepared according to the known procedure ("Organic Synthesis", Coll. Vol. I, p. 181). 2-Hydroxy-5-chloro- and 3-chloro-4-hydroxy-benzaldehydes were prepared in 26% and 12% yield respectively by the Reimer-Tiemann reaction from *p*-chlorophenol and *o*-chlorophenol, which were methylated by dimethyl sulphate and caustic soda to the corresponding methoxyaldehydes. 3:4-Dichlorobenzaldehyde was of Eastman's practical grade.

The condensation of aldehyde with sodium cyanoacetate was effected as described in "Organic Synthesis" (*loc. cit.*): Yields of cyanoacrylic acids were quantitative.

The acrylic acids were converted by the Fischer-Speier method into their esters, which were also directly obtained by the condensation of aldehydes with ethyl cyanoacetate in presence of piperidine. The dicyano compound was prepared from the ester and was hydrolysed to the succinic acid. In the preparation of 2-methoxy-5-chloro- and 3-chloro-4-methoxy-phenylsuccinic acids, the method of Dave *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) was used, while in the case of 3:4-dichlorophenylsuccinic acid, the known method was used ("Organic Synthesis", Coll. Vol. I, p. 451). Yields of succinic acids were quantitative. The succinic acids and their derivatives are tabulated below.

TABLE I*

Name of the compound.	M. P. or B.P. & cryst. shape	Formula.	%Chlorine.	
			Found.	Calc.
1. α -Cyano- β -2-methoxy-5-chloro-phenyl-acrylic acid	Yellow needles from acetic acid; 230°	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₃ NCl	15.1% Equiv. 234.0	15.0% 237.5
2. Ethyl ester of (1)	Needles from dil. alcohol; 96°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₃ NCl	13.2	13.4

*M. p. s' are uncorrected.

TABLE I (contd.)

Name of the compound.	M. P. or R. P. & cryst. shape.	Formula.	% Chlorine Found. Calc.	
3. 2-Methoxy-5-chlorophenyl-succinic acid	Granules from hot water ; 176°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ Cl	13.4	13.2
4. Dianilide of (3).	Shining needles from alcohol ; 178°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	8.8	8.9
5. Di- <i>p</i> -toluidide of (3)	Do ; 176°	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	8.3	8.1
6. Imide of (3)	Do ; 175°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₃ Cl	14.9	14.8
7. 2-Methoxy-5-chlorophenyl-succinic anhydride	Granules from benzene-petrol ; 131°	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₄ Cl	15.0	14.8
8. α-Cyano-β-3-chloro-4-methoxyphenyl-acrylic acid	Needles from acetic acid ; 234°	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ NCl	15.2	15.0
9. Ethyl ester of (8)	Needles from dilute alcohol ; 134°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₃ NCl	13.2	13.4
10. Ethyl αβ-dicyano-3-chloro-4-methoxyphenylpropionate	Do ; 104°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	12.4	12.5
11. 3-Chloro-4-methoxyphenyl-succinic acid	Granules from hot water ; 195°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ Cl	13.4	13.2
12. Dianilide of (11)	Shining needles from alcohol ; 192°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	9.0	18.9
13. Mono-anilide of (11)	Granules from alcohol ; 184°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₄ NCl	10.7	10.6
14. Di- <i>p</i> -toluidide of (11)	Shining needles from alcohol ; 165°	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	8.3	8.1
15. Imide of (11)	Do ; 159°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₃ Cl	14.9	14.8
16. 3-Chloro-4-methoxyphenyl-succinic anhydride	Yellow liquid ; 250°-55°/13 mm.	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₄ Cl	14.6	14.8
*17. α-Cyano-β-3 : 4-dichlorophenyl-acrylic acid	Shining needles from acetic acid ; 168°	C ₁₀ H ₆ O ₂ NCl ₂	29.5	29.4
18. Ethyl ester of (17)	Needles from alcohol ; 124°	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₂ NCl ₂	26.1	26.3
19. 3 : 4-Dichlorophenylsuccinic acid	Granules from hot water ; 205°	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄ Cl ₂	27.0	27.1
20. Mono-anilide of (19)	Needles from alcohol ; 160°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ NCl ₂	21.1	21.0
21. Dianilide of (19)	Needles from dil. alcohol ; 120°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₂	17.3	17.2
22. Di- <i>p</i> -toluidide of (19)	Needles from dil. alcohol ; 141° (decomp.)	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₂	15.9	16.1
23. Imide of (19)	Needles from dil. alcohol ; 136°	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₂ NCl ₂	29.3	29.1
24. 3 : 4-Dichlorophenylsuccinic anhydride	Micro-cryst. powder from benzene-petrol 110°	C ₁₀ H ₆ O ₃ Cl ₂	28.8	29.0

* Chem. Abs., 1956, 50, 15577; Ethyl. Corp. Brit. Pat., 737, 753/1955 report m.p. 168-9°.

Thanks of the authors are due to the Gujarat University for the award of a research fellowship (to D.K.G.) and a research grant (to J.J.T.).